

FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA AND ITS TREATMENT IN CHILDREN

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Annotation: Functional dyspepsia in a child is a complex of symptoms, including persistent or intermittent pain or discomfort in the epigastric region (upper abdomen), a feeling of fullness and bloating after eating, early satiety, nausea, vomiting, occurring for 12 weeks during the last 12 months, during which the examination process fails to detect any organic disease. Functional dyspepsia is a heterogeneous symptom complex with a high prevalence for general practitioners. Its frequency is also high in pediatric practice.

Keywords: epigastric, stomach fullness, regurgitation, nausea, vomiting, symptoms, dyskinetic.

Introduction

According to the modern definition, functional dyspepsia is a symptom complex that is diagnosed in children of all ages and is manifested by pain and discomfort in the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract, epigastric region (may be associated with food intake or manifest itself independently of it); characterized by a feeling of stomach fullness, regurgitation, nausea, vomiting, intolerance to fatty foods, milk, etc., lasts at least 12 weeks for one year, while a comprehensive comprehensive laboratory and instrumental examination does not reveal any organic pathology from the gastrointestinal -intestinal tract.

Based on the variety of clinical manifestations of the symptom complex, based on the so-called. "Rome III" criteria developed a new classification of functional dyspepsia. In accordance with it, the clinical forms of functional dyspepsia are: "ulcer-like", reflux-like, dyskinetic and nonspecific.

The "ulcer-like" form of functional dyspepsia is manifested by a symptom complex of an irritated stomach: pain in the epigastric region, which is associated with food intake, sometimes night pains.

The main symptoms of a reflux-like form are: regurgitation, belching, heartburn, vomiting, sour taste in the mouth.

In the dyskinetic form, patients note a feeling of heaviness in the stomach, a feeling of rapid satiety, nausea, vomiting, flatulence, intolerance to fatty foods and milk.

In the case of a non-specific form, it is difficult to classify belonging to any of the above forms.

Of the reasons leading to functional dyspepsia, the following should be noted: emotional overexertion, mental stress, eating disorders, heavy physical exertion, smoking, drinking alcohol from an early age. In children, functional dyspepsia is often associated with medication and food allergies.

The leading role in the pathogenesis of the disease belongs to impaired motility of the upper gastrointestinal tract (which in children is manifested by gastroduodenal reflux), weakness and insufficiency of sphincters, various combinations of hypo-, hyperkinetic and tonic dyskinesias. These manifestations are associated with impaired autonomic innervation and neurohumoral regulation. The intensity of the manifestation of the disease in children depends on the level of acid production in the stomach. The role of infection (*Helicobacter pylori*) is currently considered controversial.

Another direction in the development of the disease is irritable bowel syndrome. In such cases, the main manifestations are abdominal pain, periodic constipation or diarrhea, a feeling of dissatisfaction after defecation, vegetative-vascular dystonia.

The main manifestations of functional dyspepsia in childhood: gastroesophageal reflux, regurgitation, rumination, cyclic (functional) vomiting, aerophagia.

With gastroesophageal reflux, retrograde reflux occurs, the reverse movement of chyme from the stomach and / or intestines into the esophagus. Reflux can be physiological. Pathological reflux is associated with a violation of neuroregulatory mechanisms or is a manifestation of organic pathology.

In the genesis of gastroesophageal reflux, the leading role belongs to a decrease in the tone of the lower esophageal sphincter and an increase in intragastric pressure. High acidity in the stomach plays an additional role and is of major importance in damage to the esophageal mucosa.

As a result, there is a transformation of the developed reflux esophagitis and other lesions (aspiration of food into the airways, damage to the oral mucosa as a result of the reflux of acidic stomach contents) from functional to organic pathology. Among the functional diseases of childhood, the most common pathology is regurgitation (regurgitation) - the return of food masses shortly after eating. In the first months after birth, regurgitation in children is considered a physiological manifestation if it occurs rarely, in small quantities and within 1 hour after feeding.

The causes of regurgitation are as follows: the anatomical and physiological features of the upper gastrointestinal tract and the immaturity of the neurohumoral regulation of sphincters and gastric motility. Although at this age,

regurgitation is considered a pathology if it is repeated several times a day, it is abundant and develops 1 hour after feeding or later. Regurgitation is due to malnutrition, excess food, or damage to the central nervous system.

Rumination is periodic paroxysmal contractile movements of the abdominal muscles, diaphragm and tongue, which leads to the release of gastric contents into the oral cavity, which the child chews and swallows again. Usually manifests itself in the period from 3 to 8 months and does not depend on the type of food. There are no signs of discomfort.

Cyclic (functional) vomiting is an acute bout of vomiting. Attacks can last from several hours to several days with periods of remission. It occurs mainly in children over the age of 3 years and indicates severe damage to the central nervous system.

Aerophagia is the swallowing of air, which causes secondary belching and flatulence. Moderate aerophagia is often found among children during the first month after birth and is due to the immaturity of the nervous regulation of the swallowing process. Aerophagia is more common in premature and immature infants. Children older than a year in the case of aerophagia are shown a neurological examination. Aerophagia can also be caused by talking while eating, drinking too much soda, etc.

More often there is such a functional pathology as insufficiency of the cardia (chalasia of the cardia, insufficiency of the lower esophageal sphincter). In newborns, there is no pronounced anatomical sphincter at the junction of the esophagus to the stomach. The closure of the cardia occurs due to the Gubarev apparatus, in the functioning of which the angle of His plays an important role. In healthy infants, this angle is less than 90°. Its increase leads to a violation of the closure of the cardia and to insufficiency of the lower valve of the esophagus. In cases of functional diseases, accurate diagnosis is very important. To do this, a comprehensive laboratory and instrumental examination should be carried out in order to exclude organic pathology. Diseases of this type include: pyloric stenosis, gastric and / or duodenal ulcer, chronic gastritis and gastroduodenitis, reflux esophagitis, cholelithiasis, chronic pancreatitis, liver disease, etc.

The diagnosis is based on the following data (indicators):

- Anamnesis. It is necessary to identify the prerequisites for the development of the disease, hereditary predisposition, socio-economic and psychological nuances of the child's life.
- Ultrasound examination of the abdominal organs
- Coproscopy

- Analysis of feces for occult blood
- General blood analysis
- The activity of pancreatic enzymes in the blood and urine
- Biochemical tests

If necessary, if the diagnosis of a functional disease is in doubt, it is also necessary to perform:

- Endoscopy
- pH-metry of gastric juice
- X-ray examination
- Serological testing for the detection of antibodies

After establishing the diagnosis, based on etiopathogenesis, the treatment of functional dyspepsia should be based on the following principles:

- Correction of psycho-neurological status, elimination of provoking factors, treatment of concomitant diseases
- Motility correction
- Correction of disorders caused by dysmotility

Conclusion

As already noted, the main role in the treatment of functional dyspepsia is given to the correction of motor skills. Motility correction involves adherence to the regimen, diet therapy and drug treatment with prokinetics (domperidone) and antisecretory drugs (H₂-histamine receptor blockers and proton pump inhibitors).

The main drug from the group of prokinetics recommended for use in childhood is Doprokin (domperidone) "World Medicine", England. It is a blocker of dopamine receptors (D₂) and is characterized by antagonism towards peripheral dopamine receptors. Unlike Cerucal, Doprokin does not penetrate the blood-brain barrier and therefore is characterized by fewer side effects, unlike other centrally acting dopamine receptor blockers.

When using Doprokin in newborns, it is necessary to strictly adhere to the dosing regimen due to the immaturity and permeability of their blood-brain barrier.

Doprokin increases the tone of the lower esophageal sphincter, enhances gastric peristalsis, accelerates gastric emptying, and improves antro-duodenal coordination. Doprokin is widely used in pediatric practice. It is prescribed at 2.5 mg (1/4 tablet) / per 10 kg of body weight 3 times a day for 1-2 months. Side effects (headache, general weakness, drowsiness) occur in 0.5-1.8% of cases.

Contraindications to the appointment of Doprokin: hypersensitivity to domperidone; bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract; mechanical intestinal obstruction or perforation; prolactin-producing pituitary tumor.

In the case of an ulcer-like form, antisecretory drugs (for example, Ulsepan) and antacids (for example, Simalgel) are used.

With a non-specific form, symptomatic treatment is carried out (taking into account the leading symptoms) with prokinetics, enzyme preparations, antacids. The duration of treatment, physiotherapy, spa treatment are also important.

Drug treatment of chalazia cardia is aimed at strengthening the sphincter of the cardia: cholinomimetics are prescribed - bethancol at a dose of 0.2 mg / kg of body weight 3 times a day and a dopamine receptor blocker - domperidone (Doprokin) at a dose of 1 mg / kg of body weight 3 times a day 30 minutes before food.

The prognosis of the disease is favorable, although if the condition was not corrected in a timely manner, the transformation of a functional disease into an organic form is possible.

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